

Example Data Management Plan – concise version

Developmental predictors of anxiety in childhood and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on self-reported anxiety behaviours in young adults

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Concise version

Organisation
ELIXIR-UK

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Based on

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I. Data areas and data types

This study will use existing, publicly available datasets from the Millennium Cohort Study (MCS), held by the UK Data Service. We will also generate documentation including protocols, reports, and statistical models.

II. Standards and metadata

The source data is accompanied by rich metadata and documentation outlining the coding schemas used by the original researchers. Our analyses will utilise the same variable coding system to ensure consistency with the original study. We will additionally include robust documentation describing our methodology, inclusion/exclusion criteria, scripts, and methods of statistical analyses. We will generate comprehensive metadata to enhance data reusability. We will share all statistical models and macros with those who request access. The source MCS data is openly available to all.

III. Relationship to other data available in public repositories

This secondary analysis study will use existing data from the UK Data Service. We will examine Millennium Cohort Study (MCS) data – a longitudinal population study following approximately 19000 young people born across the UK from 2000-2002.

IV. Secondary use

We anticipate that our findings will be of interest to other researchers working in related field(s) both nationally and internationally. It may also be of interest to external stakeholders such as those working in child and adolescent mental health services, education and healthcare.

V. Methods for data sharing

The source data is publicly available through the UK Data Service. We will share our methodology - including statistical models and associated scripts/macros - and results through publication(s) in an open-access journal(s). We will include a clear Data Availability Statement within all publications highlighting that additional data is freely available upon request to the corresponding author(s). We will use persistent identifiers wherever possible to enhance findability. In addition, we will present our findings at local meetings

as well as national and international conferences. We will also engage with the University Press Office and the MCS Research Team at UCL to create a press release if the findings are of significant public interest.

VI. Proprietary data

We do not anticipate any restrictions to data sharing.

VII. Timeframes

Our analyses and associated documentation will be available at the point of publication, to enable maximal reuse by others. Source data is openly available from the UK Data Service. We will endeavour to respond to data access requests in a responsible and timely manner.

VIII. Format of the final dataset

Source data and associated documentation are available from the UK Data Service as .tab, .sav, .dta, .xls, .doc, and .pdf files. For consistency, we will also store our data, analyses and metadata in these formats. The datasets will not contain any identifiable information.